

BEHAVIOUR OF A LAMINATE FACED BY CERAMIC POWDER SUBJECT TO BALLISTIC IMPACT

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents some experimental aspects of the behaviour of composite materials faced by a layer of ceramic powder several millimeters thick under ballistic impact conditions. After a phenomenological description of the event, relevant aspects of the penetration process are discussed. The conclusions show the role of the ceramic powder material in this kind of protection.

INTRODUCTION

The mixed protection against projectile impact provided by ceramic tiles - a few millimeters thick-bonded on a laminate, has proven very efficient in the case of impact of low caliber ammunition (kinetic energies below one thousand joules). In previous reports [1,2] experimental results for this type of armour configuration were presented, and a simplified model was proposed [3] to analyze the phenomenon in a simplified manner.

The penetration process of a projectile in a mixed ceramic/metal or ceramic/laminate can be divided into several stages, depending on the deformation mechanisms and rupture modes of the materials involved. Experimentally, in the case of ceramic tiles bonded on a metallic plate, Reijer [4] showed, using X-ray technique, that there is a first stage in the impact process during which the ceramic material prevents projectile tip advance. A strong velocity gradient appears in the projectile: the velocity at its tip being close to zero while the rear zone of the projectile is still moving at the initial impact velocity. The duration of this first stage [4] may be approximated as the time taken for the travelling compression waves to reach the ceramic-backing plate interface, plus the time taken by cracks produced at the ceramic-backing plate interface to reach the free surface of the impacted ceramic tile. After this stage a cone of fractured ceramic material is formed which transmits the force exerted by the projectile to the backing plate. Some of the available analytical models [5,6,7] do not consider the afore-mentioned first stage, whereas others [3,4] do. The question therefore arises, how important is the first stage in the impact process?

The duration of the first stage [4] may be roughly computed as six times the time taken by the compression waves to travel from the stagnation point to the ceramic-backing plate interface. During this stage the projectile suffers a very high defeating force, and in the subsequent stage the projectile erosion starts, i.e., a loss of projectile mass occurs with physical separation of projectile parts.

Mixed ceramic/metallic and ceramic/laminate armours are expensive due to the high price of ceramic tiles. Since ceramic powder is much less expensive, its use in place of intact ceramic tiles becomes a very desirable goal. This would be feasible if new armours using ceramic powder had an areal density (weight of the armour per square meter) similar to that of the ceramic tiles/laminate armours. In this new type of mixed armour (ceramic powder bonded on a metallic or a laminate

backing plate) the first stage of the projectile penetration process does not exist, and the fractured ceramic cone is formed immediately upon projectile impact. If the first stage were not important, the impact behaviour of the two kinds of armours considered above would be similar.

Another interesting aspect is the difference in laminate failure modes which appear when the projectile strikes the laminate directly as compared to its impact on a laminate faced with ceramic powder.

To study the importance of the first stage described in the penetration process and to evaluate the possibility of using ceramic powder instead of ceramic tiles, a set of full-scale firing tests were performed. In this paper preliminary experimental results are presented together with a phenomenological description.

PROCEDURES, MATERIALS AND PROJECTILES

a) Procedures:

The experiments were carried out by firing low caliber projectiles against armours consisting of a ceramic powder layer 6 millimeters thick backed by a laminate plate, or the laminate alone. In both cases another laminate panel was placed 7 mm. from the rear face of the armours, with an air gap between the armour and the laminate panel. The configuration of the first type of armour (ceramic powder-laminate-air gap-laminate panel) is shown in Figure 1. After a shot was fired on this protection, the ceramic powder layer was removed and a second shot was fired against a zone apparently not affected by the first impact. The location of this second shot was selected on inspecting the target after the first shot. From preliminary tests a minimum distance of about 10 cm between the two shots was determined to be sufficient to prevent shot interaction. This procedure allowed a comparison of the laminate responses in both cases. After the tests the deformed projectiles were recovered.

b) Materials:

The ceramic powders used were silicon carbide of size about 0.18 or 2.00 mm. The ceramic particles were obtained by crushing whole silicon carbide tiles, and thus were very sharp. The laminates (polyethylene fibre-reinforced polyethylene matrix) were made in our laboratory using Dyneema balanced fabrics [8]. The fabric was pre-impregnated with a polyethylene matrix. A similar unidirectional polyethylene fibre/polyethylene matrix laminate (UD66 [8]) was also utilized in the experiments. The curing process was carried out by pressing (25 kg/cm²) the pack of plies for 20 minutes at 120 °C. The fibre directions was the same in all the plies.

c) Projectiles:

Two types of low caliber projectiles were used: the 7.62 mm NATO and the 9 mm Parabellum, the energy of the first ranging between 720 and 750 joules and the other between 581 and 700 joules. Both projectiles had a lead core encased in a brass jacket.

FIGURE 1

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The experimental results are shown in Table 1, in which the projectile type, the type of armour and the traumas (residual deformation of the rear face of the last laminate panel in the direction of impact) are summarized. In all tests the ceramic powder size was 0.18 mm except in tests No. 14 and 15 in which the size was larger (2 mm). In Figure 2, two photographs of the front (a) and rear (b) parts of the armour (ceramic powder layer on a laminate) used in test No. 1 show the hole produced by the 7.62 mm projectile. Figure 3 is a photograph of a 9 mm Parabellum projectile before and after impacting directly on the laminate (test No. 13) with no ceramic powder layer. Figure 4 is a photograph of the final state of the projectile in test No. 10 in which the laminate was faced by the ceramic powder layer. Figure 5 shows the projectile used in test No. 15 in which the ceramic powder size differed from that of test No. 10. The final state of the laminate in tests No. 8 and 9 is shown in Figure 6. In test No. 8 the projectile impacted on the ceramic powder layer, whereas in test No. 9 the impact occurred directly on the laminate. Figures 7 (a) and (b) are enlargements of Figure 6; they show the different laminate responses when the ceramic powder layer is facing the laminate (Figure 7 (a)) or when that layer is removed (Figure 7 (b)).

TABLE 1. Experimental results

Test No.	PROJECTILE		Ceramic powder layer	No. PLIES		Backing plate	TRAUMA (mm)	
	type	velocity (m/s)		backing plate	laminate panel		backing plate	laminate panel
1	7.62	764	yes	40	40	dyneema fabric	-perforation-	
4	9mm	415	yes	35	30	UD66	10.7	3.3
5	9mm	407	yes	30	25	UD66	13.0	5.6
6	9mm	415	not	30	25	UD66	13.4	6.3
8	9mm	415	yes	40	40	dyneema fabric	13.2	2.1
9	9mm	416	not	40	40	dyneema fabric	16.7	4.8
10	9mm	414	yes	30	25	dyneema fabric	13.8	7.0
11	9mm	407	not	30	25	dyneema fabric	17.9	10.0
12	9mm	412	yes	35	30	dyneema fabric	12.1	5.9
13	9mm	-	not	35	30	dyneema fabric	11.6	7.5
14 (*)	9mm	420	yes	30	25	dyneema fabric	15.2	5.6
15 (*)	9mm	420	yes	30	25	dyneema fabric	15.7	8.2

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

The first point of interest is the possibility of using this new mixed armour (ceramic powder layer facing a laminate) instead of the usual type: a laminate faced by intact ceramic tiles. In test No. 1 the areal density of the armour using ceramic powder was exactly the same as that of the armour made with intact ceramic tiles [1,2] and capable of defeating the 7.62 mm NATO projectile. However, the new mixed armour was clearly perforated by the projectile (test No. 1). This illustrates the importance of the first stage of the penetration process and suggests that the use of a thicker layer of ceramic powder might be necessary to defeat this projectile by giving the armour a higher areal density.

The second point of interest is the state of the recovered projectile. With the ceramic powder layer, the projectiles are flattened at their tips (see Figure 4), and the brass jacket is sometimes broken. When the projectile impacts directly on the laminate the recovered projectile is not flattened at the tip (see Figure 3). In both armour configurations the remainder of the projectile mass is unchanged. This means that erosion effects are unimportant with respect to the size of ceramic powder used in most of the tests. However, when the ceramic particles are larger, the projectile may be eroded, as shown in Figure 5.

The third point concerns the behaviour and failure of the laminate. Figure 6, and its corresponding enlargements (figures 7 (a) and (b)), show the different perforation holes produced in the armour which includes the ceramic powder layer (shot No. 8) vs. the armour lacking the layer (shot No. 9). In the first case the hole is circular whereas in the second it is square. It seems that the influence of the anisotropic behaviour of the laminate on its failure mode is more important when the laminate is directly impacted by the projectile than when it is faced by ceramic powder. Finally, the influence of the ceramic powder layer on the reduction of trauma, compared to that which occurs when the laminate is directly impacted by the projectile, may be seen in Table 1. Trauma reductions ranging from 12% (tests No. 5 and 6) to 44% (tests No. 8 and 9) can be achieved by the use of the ceramic powder layer.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

The aim of this paper has been to report some phenomenological aspects of the behaviour of ceramic powder layer/laminate armours. In subsequent phases of this research, an analytical and a full-numerical simulation of the problem will be carried out.

The main conclusions of this work are:

- 1.- The first stage of the penetration process of a projectile in a mixed armour, consisting of intact ceramic tiles bonded on a composite material, is important to the ballistic efficiency of the armour.
- 2.- The projectiles recovered after the firing tests were flattened at their tips after impacting the ceramic powder faced laminate.
- 3.- The projectile erosion effect is a function of the size of the ceramic particles: a size below 0.2 mm does not produce visible projectile erosion.
- 4.- The failure mode of the laminate depends on the presence or absence of the ceramic powder layer, which indicates that the laminate response is greatly influenced by the ceramic powder layer.

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FIGURE 2 (a)

FIGURE 2 (b)

FIGURE 3

